

DEVELOPMENT AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF A SUSTAINABLE BLUETOOTH-CONTROLLED LED MATRIX SCOREBOARD FOR REAL-TIME SPORTS APPLICATIONS

Babatunde A. IYAOMOLERE*, Oluwaseun O. OLUWASEGUN, Dennis E. TAIWO, and Omotade E. ORIDUPA

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology,
Okitipupa, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: ba.iyaomolere@oaustech.edu.ng

Abstract

This study presents the design and experimental performance evaluation of a sustainable Bluetooth-controlled Light Emitting Diode (LED) matrix scoreboard developed for real time sporting events in university environments. The system was designed to address common limitations of conventional scoreboards, including unreliable grid power, high maintenance requirements, and elevated operational costs. It comprises four P4 64×32 RGB LED panels driven by an ESP32 microcontroller for Bluetooth communication and an Arduino Nano for display control, synchronized with a DS3231 real time clock module. Power is supplied by four 18650 lithium ion batteries connected in parallel and regulated through a charge and discharge control module, while solar input enhances energy sustainability and reduces grid dependence. Experimental evaluation included Bluetooth connectivity tests conducted at 10 meter intervals in indoor and outdoor environments to assess connection stability and data accuracy, and battery performance tests involving charge and discharge cycles with voltage readings taken at 30 minute and 60 minute intervals respectively. Results showed stable Bluetooth operation up to 25 meters indoors and 20 meters outdoors, with the battery attaining full charge in 4.5 hours via AC mains and 6.5 hours under solar input, supporting approximately 50 minutes of continuous operation per cycle. The findings confirm that the scoreboard offers a portable, energy efficient, and reliable solution for university sports applications, providing a practical model for sustainable and replicable smart campus infrastructure.

Keywords
Solar Power,
Bluetooth,
LED Matrix
Display,
Scoreboard,
Energy Efficiency,
Sports

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for energy-efficient and reliable solutions in sporting infrastructure, particularly within university campuses, calls for innovative approaches to overcome challenges such as erratic power supply, high operational costs, and maintenance issues [1]. In many regions, including those with developing infrastructure, electronic devices like scoreboards often rely on grid electricity, which is frequently unavailable or unreliable. This is especially problematic in university campuses located in areas where power outages and inconsistent grid supply are common [2]. In this context, traditional scoreboards, although effective, are not always viable due to their dependence on grid power. This disrupts sporting events and significantly raises maintenance and operational costs. Furthermore, the harsh environmental conditions often encountered in outdoor settings coupled with the unreliability of the electrical grid, create additional challenges for the sustainability of these systems [3]. Therefore, there is a growing need for innovative, off-grid solutions that can ensure consistent performance while being more cost-effective and sustainable.

Solar energy presents a promising solution to these challenges, particularly in regions that experience high levels of solar radiation throughout the year. In university campuses, where activities are frequently held outdoors, integrating solar power into systems such as scoreboards can reduce reliance on the national grid and minimize operational costs. Solar power is not only a sustainable energy source but also a means of reducing the carbon footprint of electronic systems [4]. It is widely regarded as an essential energy alternative, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where a significant portion of the population still lacks reliable access to electricity [5]. The integration of solar energy into a wireless-controlled LED matrix scoreboard can offer a practical, off-grid solution for sporting events in university settings, reducing long-term costs while promoting sustainability.

In addition to energy integration, research on display systems and wireless technologies has advanced in recent years, providing insights for sustainable scoreboard development. [6] demonstrated a solar-powered, microcontroller-based LED display system, emphasizing renewable energy as a viable alternative to grid-powered devices. Similarly, [7] presented the design of a microcontroller-based moving message display, highlighting the cost-effectiveness and adaptability of programmable systems for dynamic information delivery. Wireless transmission protocols also continue to evolve; [8] evaluated LoRa's performance in diverse conditions, confirming its suitability for energy-constrained wireless communication systems. Meanwhile, [9] investigated micro-LED power efficiency, showing how chip optimization can reduce consumption in high-brightness displays, while [10] explored luminance optimization under varied ambient light, reinforcing the importance of visibility and readability in outdoor display environments. Complementary to these works, [11] discussed business models for solar-powered signage, underlining the broader economic and sustainability context of such systems.

Additional innovations have further expanded the design space for LED-based displays. [12] proposed a hybrid scrolling message display with Bluetooth control via Arduino Nano, illustrating the integration of mobile applications for flexible management. [13] demonstrated an early solar-powered 5×7 LED matrix scrolling board, providing evidence for renewable-powered scrolling displays. [14] developed an IoT-based LED display for real-time communication, while [15] advanced wireless automation using LoRa and server integration, which provides lessons for remote scoreboard control. Similarly, [16] and [17] both presented dot-matrix display systems with emphasis on wireless operation and scoreboard applications, validating the effectiveness of LED matrix technology in both academic and sporting contexts. Collectively, these studies demonstrate that the integration of solar energy, wireless communication, and microcontroller platforms into LED matrix displays offers a robust pathway for designing scoreboards that are not only energy-efficient but also adaptable to university infrastructure challenges.

Although prior studies have explored solar-powered and wireless display systems, most existing designs remain constrained by limited scalability, inefficient energy management, and dependence on grid backup power. These shortcomings hinder their reliability for sustained outdoor operation in university settings, particularly in developing regions where unstable electricity supply and high maintenance costs persist. Consequently, there is a clear research gap in developing an energy-autonomous, remotely controlled scoreboard optimized for sustainability, visibility, and performance under local environmental conditions.

This study therefore aims to design, construct, and evaluate a solar-powered, wireless-controlled LED matrix scoreboard specifically suited to university campuses. The objectives are to:

- (i) develop a solar-powered microcontroller-based LED matrix display;
- (ii) integrate wireless functionality for real-time score updates; and
- (iii) assess the system's energy efficiency, operational reliability, and cost-effectiveness.

The outcome is expected to advance sustainable electronic display design and provide a replicable framework for off-grid scoreboard applications in educational environments.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the Materials and Methods. Section 3 presents the Results and Discussion. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Overview of the System

The wireless-controlled LED matrix scoreboard is designed for real-time score updates in sporting events. The system architecture is composed of three key components: the ESP32 microcontroller, the Arduino Nano microcontroller, and the LED matrix display. The ESP32 is responsible for the Bluetooth wireless communication with the mobile app, while the Arduino Nano is used to drive the LED matrix display. The ESP32 and Arduino Nano communicate via a serial connection to update the scoreboard based on the commands received from the mobile app. A functional block diagram of the system is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. System Architecture of Bluetooth-controlled Scoreboard

2.2 Hardware Components

2.2.1 Display Unit

The display unit utilized in this system is a 64×32 P4 RGB LED matrix panel, characterized by a 4 mm pixel pitch and high pixel density, offering sufficient brightness for outdoor visibility. The matrix comprises 2048 individual RGB LEDs, each addressable for full-color output and controlled via a microcontroller to enable smooth visual transitions at a refresh rate of 60 Hz. Electrical connections include dedicated pins for red, green, and blue color channels (R1, G1, B1, R2, G2, B2), row addressing (A, B, C, D), clock (CLK), output enable (OE), latch (LAT), and ground (GND), as well as a power input through VCC and GND terminals. The module supports cascading of multiple panels, in accordance with standard modular LED matrix design principles.

2.2.2 ESP32 Microcontroller

The ESP32 microcontroller was employed to facilitate Bluetooth communication between the user interface (mobile application) and the display system. Its Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) functionality offers low power consumption and stable wireless connectivity over a typical range of up to 30 meters, making it well-suited for applications in dynamic environments such as sports scoring. Programmed using the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE), the ESP32 utilizes the Arduino BLE library for managing communication protocols. Its multi-functional pin configuration enables straightforward interfacing with peripheral devices, including the LED matrix and secondary microcontrollers.

2.2.3 Arduino Nano Microcontroller

The Arduino Nano serves as the dedicated controller for managing LED matrix operations. It receives score updates and control commands from the ESP32 through a serial communication interface and transmits data to the LED display using the I2C communication protocol. Its compact size, low power requirements, and ease of integration render it suitable for embedded display control applications. This layered configuration, combining the ESP32 for wireless data transmission and the Arduino Nano for direct display management, ensures reliable and efficient system performance.

2.2.4 Power Supply Unit

The power system comprises two primary energy sources: a 12 V DC solar input and a 5 V DC, 800 mA electrical supply, both utilized to recharge the system's battery. These inputs are interfaced through a 3-series Battery Management System (3S BMS), which provides essential protective functions including overcharge and over-discharge prevention, short-circuit protection, and cell voltage balancing. This regulation ensures the safety, efficiency, and longevity of the energy storage subsystem. The regulated current from the BMS charges a parallel-connected lithium-ion battery pack composed of 18650 cells, from which power is subsequently distributed to the various components on the circuit board, enabling reliable system operation.

2.3 Software Configuration

The software architecture was implemented using the Arduino IDE, which provided an integrated environment for programming both the ESP32 and Arduino Nano microcontrollers. The Adafruit GFX and LED Matrix libraries facilitated matrix control, while Bluetooth communication on the ESP32 was established using the Arduino BLE library. This configuration enabled efficient and low-latency data exchange between the mobile application and the LED matrix, ensuring reliable real-time updates on the scoreboard.

A dedicated mobile application, compatible with Android and iOS platforms, was developed to serve as the user interface for remote operation. The app allows users to input and modify scores, reset displays, and manage timing functions. Data transmitted via Bluetooth are received by the ESP32, decoded, and forwarded to the Arduino Nano, which executes the corresponding display operations on the LED matrix.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the communication sequence begins with the user initiating Bluetooth connectivity and transmitting data through the mobile interface. The Arduino module subsequently handles data reception, processing, and flashing of the updated information to the LED board. This structured workflow enhances system responsiveness, communication reliability, and overall energy efficiency.

Figure 2. Flow diagram of Bluetooth-control scoreboard communication system

2.4 Hardware and Software Integration

The hardware and software integration phase ensured the seamless interaction of all system modules to achieve a robust and fully functional scoreboard unit. The assembly process followed the detailed circuitry layouts presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4, which illustrate the signal connections and power distribution networks of the system. The ESP32 microcontroller was configured to handle Bluetooth communication and command reception, while the Arduino Nano managed the LED matrix display through the I²C interface. This dual-microcontroller architecture enhanced processing efficiency and modularity. A Real-Time Clock (RTC) DS3231 module was also incorporated to provide precise timekeeping, ensuring that match durations and real-time scores were accurately maintained throughout operation.

As shown in Figure 5, the hardware assembly involved the interconnection of all major components, including the ESP32, Arduino Nano, RTC module, power management circuitry, and LED display panel, all housed within a compact and durable frame. The completed system, illustrated in Figure 6, represents the developed LED matrix

scoreboard, demonstrating the integration of electronic, mechanical, and communication subsystems into a cohesive prototype.

The software deployment stage entailed uploading the compiled firmware to both microcontrollers via the Arduino IDE, followed by Bluetooth pairing between the mobile application and the ESP32. Communication parameters were configured to ensure secure and reliable wireless data exchange. Calibration of the LED matrix display was then performed to optimize brightness, refresh rate, and communication frequency, achieving smooth and responsive display performance. The mobile application interface, shown in Figure 7, provides an intuitive control environment through which users can update scores, reset displays, and manage timing operations in real time.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the scoreboard control circuit

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the scoreboard power circuit

Figure 5. Hardware Assembly of the integrated system

Figure 6. Developed LED matrix scoreboard prototype

Figure 7. Mobile application interface for scoreboard control

2.5 System Performance Evaluation

The performance of the developed system was assessed by evaluating Bluetooth connectivity and battery efficiency through controlled experimental procedures. The Bluetooth test involved transmitting data from the

mobile application to the LED matrix scoreboard at 10 m intervals under both indoor and outdoor conditions. Signal accuracy, response time, and display reliability were observed to determine the consistency of data transmission across varying distances. Results confirmed stable communication within the short-range operational limit, demonstrating effective wireless control in diverse environments. The battery performance test involved systematic charging and discharging assessments, with voltage readings recorded at 30-minute and 1-hour intervals, respectively. These measurements provided insights into the charging duration, discharge behaviour, and overall energy efficiency of the lithium-ion power subsystem, establishing its adequacy in sustaining reliable operation of the scoreboard over multiple duty cycles.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents results on Bluetooth connectivity functionality at incremental distances and examines the battery’s charging and discharging rates, assessing overall system viability in typical university sports applications.

3.1 Bluetooth Connectivity Result

The Bluetooth connectivity evaluation was conducted to determine the communication reliability and effective transmission range of the ESP32 microcontroller under controlled indoor and outdoor conditions, as presented in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. In the indoor tests, the system sustained stable connectivity and full functional response up to a range of 25 m, after which intermittent communication occurred at 30 m and complete disconnection at 35 m. Under outdoor conditions, stable operation was maintained up to 20 m, followed by a progressive decline in signal quality and total loss beyond 30 m. These outcomes demonstrate that Bluetooth technology offers dependable short-range wireless communication suitable for localized scoreboard control within enclosed or moderately open environments. The observed range attenuation at greater distances reflects the intrinsic limitations of Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) transmission, primarily influenced by multipath interference, signal absorption, and environmental noise, thereby defining the effective operational boundary for consistent and latency-free data exchange.

Table 1. Bluetooth performance for Indoor environment

Distance (m)	Connect	Function
0	✓	✓
5	✓	✓
10	✓	✓
15	✓	✓
20	✓	✓
25	✓	✓
30	✓	×
35	✓	×

Table 2. Bluetooth performance for Outdoor environment

Distance (m)	Connect	Function
0	✓	✓
5	✓	✓
10	✓	✓
15	✓	✓
20	✓	✓
25	✓	×
30	✓	×
35	×	×

3.2 Battery Performance Result

The charging and discharging characteristics of the power subsystem were evaluated to assess the energy efficiency and operational endurance of the developed scoreboard. As shown in Figure 8, the battery pack comprising four 18650 lithium-ion cells connected in parallel achieved full charge within approximately 4.5 hours when powered from AC mains and 6.5 hours under solar input, with the slower rate attributed to fluctuations in solar irradiance during testing. This demonstrates the adaptability of the hybrid charging configuration, which ensures functional reliability under varying power sources. The corresponding discharging profile in Figure 9 exhibited a steady voltage decline over time, providing an average operational duration of about 50 minutes per cycle before reaching the discharge threshold. These results confirm the system's energy efficiency and short-term autonomy, making it suitable for standard sporting events, while indicating that higher-capacity energy storage would be beneficial for extended operation.

Figure 8: The charging rate of the battery

Figure 9: The discharging rate of the battery

3.3 Discussion

The Bluetooth connectivity evaluation demonstrated stable indoor communication up to 25 m, after which performance declined at 30 m and failed at 35 m. In outdoor tests, stability was maintained up to 20 m, but signal degradation occurred beyond this range with complete disconnection at 30 m. These results confirm that Bluetooth provides dependable short-range communication suitable for localized scoreboard control in enclosed or moderately open environments. As reported by [18], Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) transmission is inherently limited by path loss, reflection, and interference, which explains the observed signal attenuation in this study. To

enhance applicability in larger sporting arenas, future designs could incorporate long-range protocols such as LoRa or Wi-Fi to overcome these range constraints.

The battery performance results, shown in Figures 8–9, highlight the adaptability and efficiency of the hybrid power subsystem. The battery achieved full charge in approximately 4.5 h via AC mains and 6.5 h under solar input, the latter influenced by irradiance variability consistent with observations from [19], who identified sunlight fluctuation as a critical factor affecting stability in solar-battery hybrid systems. The discharging profile exhibited a gradual voltage decline over about 50 minutes of continuous operation, confirming short-term autonomy suitable for standard match durations. Nevertheless, as emphasized by [20], expanding energy storage capacity and implementing optimized charge–discharge management would enhance operational endurance and improve system reliability during extended events.

In summary, the developed solar-powered, Bluetooth-controlled LED matrix scoreboard effectively combines renewable energy utilization with reliable wireless communication, achieving a balance between operational efficiency, sustainability, and cost performance. Its proven stability supports deployment in small- to medium-scale university facilities where grid reliability is limited. Further optimization of wireless range and battery capacity would enhance scalability, reinforcing the system's role as a replicable, energy-autonomous, and sustainable framework for smart-campus sports infrastructure.

4. CONCLUSION

This study presented the successful design, implementation, and experimental evaluation of a solar-powered, wireless-controlled LED matrix scoreboard developed to enhance energy efficiency and operational reliability in university sporting environments. The integration of renewable solar energy with Bluetooth-enabled microcontroller control established an autonomous and sustainable display architecture that mitigates dependence on unstable grid power. Empirical evaluation demonstrated stable Bluetooth connectivity of up to 25 m indoors and 20 m outdoors, confirming effective short-range wireless performance under varying ambient conditions. The power subsystem, comprising four parallel 18650 lithium-ion cells regulated through a charge–discharge control module, achieved full charge within 4.5 hours via AC mains and 6.5 hours under solar input, sustaining approximately 50 minutes of continuous operation per cycle. These results substantiate the system's functional robustness, portability, and suitability for localized sporting applications within university campuses. By leveraging low-cost components and renewable energy integration, the developed system contributes to the advancement of sustainable, intelligent, and energy-autonomous electronic display technologies. Future research should investigate the incorporation of long-range wireless communication protocols such as LoRa or Wi-Fi to enable distributed control, extended coverage, and real-time data synchronization for scalable deployment across larger sporting facilities.

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